

MEDICATION ERRORS BY NURSES AT MEDICAL-SURGICAL DEPARTMENTS OF A SAUDI HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background: Medication errors have a wide-ranging impact, affecting patients, families, healthcare personnel, hospitals, and even organizations. Medication error consequences range from no noticeable symptoms to death, and they are a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in patients. Many factors have been identified as potential causes of pharmaceutical errors. Nurses are seen as crucial players in the medication administration process, and as such, they may cause or report various types of drug errors at healthcare facilities.

Aim: The study aimed to identify the medical-surgical floor nurses' perception of medication errors at King Saud Medical City (KSMC) in terms of frequency, types, and causes.

Methods: This research used a descriptive, cross-sectional design including a convenient sample of 260 nurses working at different medical-surgical departments at KSMC in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The study utilized the Modified Gladstone scale in addition to the sociodemographic datasheet. The current study adhered to all ethical principles of scientific research.

Results: Out of the two hundred sixty participants, 35% of them reported that they had three to four years of experience in medication administration, and 31.2% of them had 5 to 9 years of nursing experience. More than one-third of the participants reported that they didn't have any medication errors during their course of work. The most frequently reported causes of medication errors were illegible physician's handwriting, followed by the wrong drug dose prescription, then the nurses' exhaustion. According to the participants, 14.32 % of the medication errors were reported officially in the hospital using incident reports. About 75% of the participants had considered the six scenarios as situations that require informing the physician, 70.65% of them believed that the scenarios require formal reporting through incident reports, while only 68.08% of them perceived the scenarios as medication errors.

Conclusion: Illegible handwriting of physicians, incorrect drug dose prescription, and nursing exhaustion were the most reported reasons of medication errors as revealed by participants; as a result, the management of those issues is crucial to reduce medication errors. Medication errors should be officially documented through incident reports. Because the percentage of reported medication error was low, hospitals must provide an open environment system for medication error reporting that is informative, confidential, and free of a penalty. It is critical to provide continuous education and on-the-job training for nurses in the hospital regarding medication administration.

Keywords: Floor nurses, King Saud Medical City, Medical-Surgical Departments, Medication errors, Riyadh, and Saudi Arabia.

Introduction

A medication error is described as "any preventable incident that may cause or contribute to inappropriate pharmaceutical usage or patient damage while the medication is under the healthcare professionals, patients, or consumers control." A medication error is a flaw in the treatment process that causes or has the potential to cause patient harm (Khan & Tidman, 2022). These occurrences could be related to professional practice, healthcare equipment, procedures, or systems (Mercer et al., 2016).

Medication errors can also be described as any mistake that occur during the prescription, preparation, administration, or follow-up of a medicine that are usually avoidable. They are caused by incorrect pharmaceutical usage by patients, health care providers, or consumers, and can be harmful to the patient (NCCMERP, 2016). The most common two major categories of drug errors identified in the literature occur during the preparation or administration stages (Agyemang & While, 2010; Dionisi et al., 2022; Isaacs et al., 2021).

Despite the rising interest in this issue around the world, the prevalence of medication errors has not decreased considerably (Chang & Mark, 2009; Mrayyan et al., 2008; Salmasi et al., 2015). Medication errors are increasing globally, and they constitute the most common cause of hospital unfavorable occurrences (Abdi et al., 2018; Agyemang & While, 2010). The prevalence of medication errors in various units and departments of a North African educational hospital found that the prevalence of medication errors in developed countries is much higher (Jennane et al., 2011).

Medication errors have a wide-ranging impact, affecting patients, families, healthcare personnel, institutions, and even communities. Medication error consequences range from no noticeable symptoms to death, and they are a significant source of patient morbidity and mortality, ranking third in the United States (Makary & Daniel, 2016). Itching, rashes, or skin deformity can occur in some situations, resulting in a new ailment that is either transient or permanent. As a result of these drug errors, many patients have costly and protracted hospital stays, and some patients never fully recover from their premorbid status (Moyen et al., 2008; Vrbnjak et al., 2016).

Many factors have been identified as potential causes of medication errors, including personal factors such as a lack of knowledge about the patients, drug order communication-related errors, such as unreadable handwriting, confusion between similar drug names, confusion in metric and dosing units, and inappropriate abbreviations (Henneman et al., 2010; World Health Organization, 2016). In addition to drug-related variables, other causes of medication errors are classed as organizational-related factors (Rodziewicz et al., 2022).

Nurses are known as crucial players in the medication administration process, and they may cause or report several types of drug errors at healthcare facilities. The perception of nurses about medication errors is not well studied in Saudi hospitals, and few recent studies on this topic have been conducted in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Al-Otaibi et al., 2018; Al Khreem & Al-khadher, 2021; Ala'a et al., 2016; Alshaikh et al., 2013; Alsulami et al., 2019; Alsulami et al., 2013), therefore, this study aimed to explore the floor nurses' perception about medication errors at King Saud Medical City.

Aim of the study

The current study aimed to identify the medical-surgical nurses' perception of medication errors at King Saud Medical City (KSMC) in Riyadh concerning the frequency, types, and causes of medication errors.

The study's objectives included investigating the participants' sociodemographic characteristics, assessing the nurses' perception of the frequency of medication errors committed in their departments, determining their perception of the percentage of medication error reporting, and investigating the types of medication errors and their causes at KSMC's medical-surgical departments.

Research questions

The study's research questions included the following: 1. What is the nurses' perception of the incidence of medication errors in their departments? 2. What is the percentage of medication errors reported? 3. What are the most prevalent types of drug errors? 4. What are the most common causes of drug errors on the medical-surgical floors of KSMC in Riyadh?

Methods and subjects

Research design

The current investigation was carried out using a descriptive, cross-sectional research design.

Research Setting

The research was conducted at various medical-surgical departments of KSMC in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. KSMC features six medical-surgical departments or floors with a considerable number of nurses. Aside from the researchers' convenience, the KSMC hospital was picked because of its vast size, large number of working staff, hospital modernism, and staff cooperation.

Sample selection

The study employed a non-random convenience sampling strategy. The study's sample consisted of all available nurses willing to participate and working at KSMC of all nationalities and genders.

At KSMC, there were approximately 800 nurses working in the medical-surgical departments and floors. According to the sample size calculation using OpenEpi software, Version 3, to achieve a power of 0.95, an alpha error of 0.5, and a medium-size effect of 0.05, the minimum number of nurses required to participate in the study was 260 nurses; thus, the selected sample in the current study included 260 nurses.

Instruments

Because English is the official language of nursing education, documentation, and communication at KSMC, a self-reporting survey was employed to collect the necessary data using the original English instrument (The Modified Gladstone's scale). In the current study, the Modified Gladstone scale was used to collect data on medication errors, including the frequency, types, and perceptions of the causes of medication errors (Mayo & Duncan, 2004). The modified form was used to collect information about the participants' demographic features (age, gender, nationality, educational level, experience, and work position).

The causes of medication errors, as perceived by nurses, were studied by ten elements assessed on a scale of 1 to 10, with 1 being the least recurrent and 10 being the most recurrent. Six clinical scenarios were used to examine nurses' perceptions of medication errors in terms of whether they were serious or not (the medication error occurred or not, whether the physician should be notified or not, and whether the incidence report should be completed or not).

In another study, the tool's reliability was assessed using the test-retest approach (Cronbach's alpha coefficient = 0.78) (Osborne et al., 1999). Because this instrument has previously been used in numerous investigations, the prior results represented the validity and reliability of this instrument which were accepted (Mrayyan & Al-Atiyat, 2011; Mrayyan et al., 2008; Mrayyan et al., 2007; Shahin et al., 2018).

Ethical considerations

Before starting this study, the Institutional Review Board of King Saud Medical City in Riyadh approved recruiting human participants (IRB reference # H1RI-18-Apr22-03). After detailing the goal and scope of the study in the questionnaire, informed consent was sought from respondents. The willingness of participants to engage in the current study and complete the questionnaire without force was deemed informed consent. All respondents voluntarily participated in the survey without coercion and were allowed to leave at any time. There were no damaging techniques or deceptions used on the respondents. By employing anonymous surveys, study participants were adequately secured against data exploitation.

Procedure and data analysis

Data was collected over two weeks in July 2022 by distributing an electronic questionnaire to nurses via social media platforms such as Emails, WhatsApp, Messenger, and other technologies. After receiving ethical approval from the research ethics committee and IRB at KSMC, data collection began.

Data from Google Forms was collected, edited, and coded before being analyzed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23.0. (IBM Corp, 2015). Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation or number and percentage, were used to present data. For continuous data, the mean and standard deviation were employed, with an alpha level of 0.05 considered significant, whilst number and percentages were utilized for categorical variables.

Results

In the current study, 260 nurses from different medical-surgical departments working at the KSMC participated in the study. For the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants, **Table 1** shows that the age of most of the participants extended from 25 years to 44 years (91%), and more than two-thirds of the participants were males (68.1%). On the other side, Bachelor's degree holders constituted most of the participants (65.4%) followed by master's degree holders (21.2%).

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of the participants (N=260)

Sociodemographic Data		n	%
Age	Less than 25 years	7	2.7%
	25–34 years	118	45.4%
	35–44 years	118	45.4%
	45–54 years	9	3.5%
	55 years or more	8	3.1%
Gender	Male	177	68.1%
	Female	83	31.9%
Level of education	Diploma	31	11.9%
	Bachelor	170	65.4%
	Master	55	21.2%

Doctorate	4	1.5%
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Table 2 reflects the perceived medication errors committed by the participants and their medication handling experience they have. Once asked about their experience in medication handling, more than one-third of the nurses (35%) reported that they had three to four years of experience in medication administration, followed by nurses who reported that they had 10 years or more of experience in medication administration (30%). In the same line, the greatest proportion of the participants reported that they had 5 to 9 years of nursing experience (31.2 %), followed by 28.1% of the participants who had ten years or more of experience, then the nurses who reported having three to four years of experience in the nursing field (27.3%).

Concerning the estimated number of medication errors committed during their nursing career, more than one-third of the participants reported that they had no medication errors (35%). However, the percentage of nurses who reported committing five medication errors was 12.3%, followed by the nurses who reported committing one medication error during their nursing career (11.5%).

Table 2. Medication errors and handling experience of the participants

Medication Errors History		n	%
How long have you been qualified to administer medications?	Less than one year	19	7.3%
	1–2 years	20	7.7%
	3–4 years	91	35.0%
	5–9 years	52	20.0%
	10 years or more	78	30.0%
How long have you been a practicing nurse?	Less than one year	8	3.1%
	1–2 years	27	10.4%
	3–4 years	71	27.3%
	5–9 years	81	31.2%
	10 years or more	73	28.1%
How many medication errors do you remember making over the course of your career?	0	91	35.0%
	1	30	11.5%
	2	27	10.4%
	3	22	8.5%
	4	15	5.8%
	5	32	12.3%
	6	21	8.1%
	7	10	3.8%
	8	4	1.5%

9	0	0.0%
10 and more	8	3.1%

Concerning the causes of medication errors as perceived by the participants, **Table 3** revealed that the most prevalent cause of medication errors was associated with the illegible handwriting of the physicians when writing on the doctor's order form, followed by the medication errors due to wrong dose prescription by physicians, then the drug errors that occur due to nurses' exhaustion ($M \pm SD = 6.43 \pm 2.74, 6.39 \pm 3.01, 6.22 \pm 2.87$ respectively).

On the other hand, the least perceived cause of medication errors by the nurses was their distraction by other patients, coworkers, or events in the unit.

Table 3. Causes of medication errors

CAUSE OF MEDICATION ERRORS	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
1. Drug errors occur when the nurse fails to check the patient's name band with the Medication Administration Record	260	1.0	10.0	6.004	2.9415
2. Drug errors occur when the physician's writing on the doctor's order form is difficult to read or illegible.	260	1.0	10.0	6.431	2.7437
3. Drug errors occur when the medication labels/packaging are of poor quality or damaged.	260	1.0	10.0	6.031	2.7154
4. Drug errors occur when there is confusion between two drugs with similar names.	260	1.0	10.0	5.888	2.7870
5. Drug errors occur when the physician prescribes the wrong dose.	260	1.0	10.0	6.385	3.0183
6. Drug errors occur when the nurse miscalculates the dose.	260	1.0	10.0	5.981	2.9715
7. Drug errors occur when the nurse sets up or adjusts an infusion device incorrectly.	260	1.0	10.0	5.919	2.8074
8. Drug errors occur when nurses are confused by the different types and functions of infusion devices.	260	1.0	10.0	5.900	2.6722
9. Drug errors occur when nurses are distracted by other patients, coworkers, or events in the unit.	260	1.0	10.0	5.665	3.0642
10. Drug errors occur when nurses get tired and exhausted.	260	1.0	10.0	6.223	2.8685

Figure 1 represents the perception of nurses about the percentage of medication errors reported in the hospital. Taking the average percent of reported medication errors, nurses reported that the percentage of reported medication errors ranged from 0% to 95%; However, the average of the reported medication errors was as low as 14.32% as perceived by the participating nurses.

Figure 1: Perception about the percentage of medication errors reporting

Giving the participants six clinical scenarios of medication errors that can be executed by nurses in their daily practice and are considered drug errors that need notifying the physician and making an incident report, the participants were asked to give their opinion on each clinical scenario in terms of whether the scenario represents drug error, does it requires notifying the physician, and whether incident reporting was necessary or not (Table 4).

In the 3rd scenario which described the error in TPN feeding infusion rate, most of the nurses reported that the scenario represented medication error (80.8%) which requires incident reporting (81.2%).

Though only 61.9% of the nurses considered the scenario as a medication error, and just 66.5% of them considered that the scenario requires incident reporting, however, the greatest proportion of the nurses considered that the 6th scenario requires notifying the physician (82.7%).

Surprisingly, the least percentage of the nurses reported that the 1st scenario was considered a medication error (56.9%). Furthermore, only 67.3% of the participants reported that the 2nd scenario required the nurse to notify the physician. Also, just 65.8% of the participants believed that the 4th clinical scenario requires official incident reporting.

From the analysis of the six scenarios, more than three-fourths of the participants in the current study (75.32%) had considered the scenarios as situations that require informing the physician, 70.65% of them believed that the scenarios require formal reporting through incident reports, while only 68.08% of them perceived the scenarios as medication errors.

Table 4. Nurses' perception of the medication errors

NURSES' PERCEPTIONS of MEDICATION ERRORS		No		Yes	
		n	%	n	%
1. A patient misses his midday dose of oral ampicillin because he was in the X-Ray for three hours.	Do you consider this a drug error?	112	43.1%	148	56.9%
	Do we need to notify the physician?	68	26.2%	192	73.8%

	Is the incident report necessary?	74	28.5%	186	71.5%
2. Four patients on a busy surgical unit receive their 6:00 pm doses of IV antibiotics 4 hours late.	Do you consider this a drug error?	72	27.7%	188	72.3%
	Do we need to notify the physician?	85	32.7%	175	67.3%
	Is the incident report necessary?	84	32.3%	176	67.7%
3. A patient receiving TPN feeding via an infusion pump is given 200 ml/hr instead of the correct rate of 125 ml/hr for the first three hours of the 24-hour infusion. The pump was reset to the correct rate after the change of shift at 7:00 am when the oncoming nurse realized that the pump was set at the incorrect rate.	Do you consider this a drug error?	50	19.2%	210	80.8%
	Do we need to notify the physician?	67	25.8%	193	74.2%
	Is the incident report necessary?	49	18.8%	211	81.2%
4. A patient admitted with status asthmaticus on 13/8/2014 at 2 am is prescribed Ventolin nebulizers every four hours. The nurse omits the 6:00 am dose on 13/8/2014 as the patient is asleep.	Do you consider this a drug error?	88	33.8%	172	66.2%
	Do we need to notify the physician?	69	26.5%	191	73.5%
	Is the incident report necessary?	89	34.2%	171	65.8%
5. A physician orders Percocet 1-2 tabs for post-op pain every 4 hours. At 4:00 pm the patient complains of pain, requests one pill, and is medicated. At 6:30 pm the patient requests the second pain pill. The nurse administers the pill.	Do you consider this a drug error?	77	29.6%	183	70.4%
	Do we need to notify the physician?	51	19.6%	209	80.4%
	Is the incident report necessary?	75	28.8%	185	71.2%
6. A patient is receiving a routine 9 am dose of digoxin every day. Yesterday's digoxin level was 1.8 (the high side of normal). A digoxin level was drawn at 6 am today. At 9 am the nurse holds the digoxin because the lab value is not available yet.	Do you consider this a drug error?	99	38.1%	161	61.9%
	Do we need to notify the physician?	45	17.3%	215	82.7%
	Is the incident report necessary?	87	33.5%	173	66.5%
Total	Do you consider this a drug error?	31.92%		68.08%	
	Do we need to notify the physician?	24.68%		75.32%	
	Is the incident report necessary?	29.35%		70.65%	

Discussion

The current study sought to determine the frequency, types, and causes of drug errors in the medical-surgical departments at KSMC as perceived by nurses there. Most of the participants in the current study were between the ages of 25 and 44, indicating an energetic and young nursing staff working in the medical-surgical departments of KSMC hospital. Females made up more than two-thirds of the participants, indicating that the nursing profession is still considered feminine in Saudi Arabia.

In terms of educational level, bachelor's degree holders made up the majority, reflecting the proper preparation and appropriate education of the nursing staff in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The sociodemographic characteristics of the current study participants most likely reflect the characteristics of nurses in the hospital and may, to some extent, reflect similar demographic characteristics of nursing staff in other governmental hospitals

in the Riyadh region, as revealed by previous studies (Almajwal, 2015; Kaddourah et al., 2018a; Kaddourah et al., 2018b).

Regarding the medication errors committed by the participants, the findings revealed a range of responses from the participants regarding the number of medication errors committed during clinical practice in the hospital, ranging from no medication errors to multiple medication errors that exceeded ten drug mistakes. However, it was obvious that more than one-third of participants reported no medication errors when working as staff nurses. The findings contradict another study conducted in Jordan, which indicated that almost 97% of the volunteers admitted to making at least one prescription error while working as a nurse in the hospital (Shahin et al., 2018). This point may also raise concerns about the issue of drug error self-reporting, which may represent nurses' fear of admitting medication errors or the shame associated with reporting medication errors made during daily practice in hospitals.

Most of the sample nurses reported having three to more than ten years of clinical experience, and they also reported having a long experience in handling medications, ranging from three to more than ten years, which confirms the satisfactory experience of the nurses in handling medications from prescription to administration and follow up, and reflects the competence of most of the participants in drug management.

The most common cause of medication errors was illegible handwriting of the physicians when drafting the doctor's prescription, followed by medication errors owing to the inappropriate drug dose provided by the physicians, and finally drug errors that occur when the nurses become fatigued and exhausted. The findings differed from those of a prior study, which discovered that the most common reasons of medication error were connected with nurses' inexperience, rushing through work, technological issues, understaffing, and patient acuity (Treiber & Jones, 2018). Furthermore, another Iranian study found that low nurse-to-patient ratio (57.3%), excessive workload (51.1%), and nurses' exhaustion (40.4%) were the most significant characteristics related with medication errors (Zarea et al., 2018).

The current study's findings emphasize the importance of writing legible physician's orders, particularly medication orders; however, transitioning to electronic medical records and having printed doctor orders can be one of the best solutions for illegible handwriting and can certainly prevent any medication error associated with drug order misinterpretation.

Furthermore, clinicians should prioritize validating an appropriately ordered drug in terms of dose and frequency to reduce medication errors. This can be accomplished by having the pharmaceutical orders double-checked with the pharmacist, Pharm. D, another physician, or even the nurse before they are administered.

On the other hand, nurses should be observed for the causes of medication errors, such as fatigue or exhaustion as a result of long work hours or consecutive working days. To accomplish this, head nurses and nurse managers should collaborate to reduce the cause of medication errors associated with nurses' exhaustion by developing nursing schedules based on standardized criteria to ensure an appropriate length of working system and appropriate assignment, duties, and responsibilities for all nursing staff.

Although the estimated percentage of reported medication errors in the current study ranged from 0% to 95%, the mean reported medication errors as perceived by nurses were as low as 14.32%. According to Shahin et al. (2018), most of participants believed that the percentage of medication errors reported to the nurse manager ranged between 51% and 80% of the overall number of medication errors, with a mean of 60.7%.

As a result, healthcare institutions and hospitals must provide a confidential, educational-open environment in which nurses and other healthcare providers can report medication errors without fear of legal ramifications and penalties, which cause nurses to avoid reporting medication errors and hide them for fear of being exposed and punished.

It is also vital to establish a medication error surveillance, follow-up, and monitoring system in hospitals to determine their causes, types, and factors in order to decrease drug errors as much as feasible.

In the current study, participants were asked to assess six scenarios based on three criteria: whether the scenario reflects a medication error or not, whether the nurse is required to notify the physician or not, and whether an

incident report is required or not. The nurses' responses revealed an acceptable level of awareness of the incorrect TPN infusion rate as a medication error requiring the completion of an incident report, with less confirmation of the need to notify the physician. Similarly, respondents recognized withholding prescribed medication without order as a situation that required telling the physician; nevertheless, the scenario was poorly recognized as a drug error that requires submitting an incident report.

Similarly, participants of the current study did not satisfactorily consider skipping a prescription dose owing to a diagnostic procedure, such as X-rays, as a medication error. Delayed drug administration was not regarded as a pharmaceutical error that required notification to the physician. Furthermore, skipping medicine dosages owing to certain circumstances, such as the patient resting, was not appropriately classified as a case requiring the creation of an incident report.

In general, more than three-fourths of the nurses in the current study thought the scenarios required informing the physician, and a smaller proportion thought the scenarios required formal reporting through incident reports, while the smallest percentage thought the scenarios were medication error events. These findings differed from the findings of a similar study conducted in Jordan, which revealed that 77% of the participating nurses perceived the six clinical scenarios to be medication errors, and that more than two-thirds of nurses (68%), believed that the events of the scenarios were supposed to be reported to the physician, while only 57% believed that a written incident report should be made for the given scenarios (Shahin et al., 2018).

Many clinical settings in the current study demonstrated a disparity in nurses' perceptions of prescription errors. Some situations depict nurses failing to classify the event as a medication error, failing to validate the need to notify the physician, and even failing to require formal reporting via an incident report. Nurses' understanding of various forms of medication errors, the significance of telling the physician to take action, and the requirement to report the event using the incident report all require the attention of nursing managers and leaders. As previously documented in studies, appropriate education should be provided to nurses, with a greater emphasis on the need of providing continuous education and on-the-job training about drug administration in the hospital (Alsulami et al., 2013; Fathi et al., 2017; Mrayyan et al., 2008; Shahin et al., 2018; Shahin, 2019).

Conclusion

The reporting of medication errors is one of the concerns that overlap with hospital patient safety. A large proportion of participants reported that they had not committed any medication errors during the course of their employment, which may, to some extent, reflect the fear of nurses to admit to committing medication errors or the stigma associated with reporting medication errors during daily hospital practice. According to the majority of nurses, the rate of reported medication errors was rather low.

According to the participants, illegible physician handwriting, prescribing the improper medicine dose, and nursing exhaustion and fatigue were the leading causes of medication errors; consequently, addressing and correcting these issues is a top priority for reducing medication errors.

Pharmaceutical error awareness in daily clinical practice is a crucial aspect in preventing, detecting, informing, and reporting medication errors via official channels. More than three-quarters of the nurses in the current study perceived the scenarios as situations that necessitate informing the physician, a smaller proportion believed that the situations necessitated formal incident reporting, and the smallest proportion perceived the scenarios as medication errors.

Recommendations:

To limit the impact of medication errors on patient safety and health, medication errors should be notified to the physician so that corrective action can be taken; additionally, medication errors must be recorded formally via

incident reports. To this end, hospitals must provide an open environment for reporting drug errors that is informative, confidential, and devoid of a punitive system.

Because illegible physicians' handwriting, incorrect dose prescriptions, and nurse exhaustion were identified as the primary causes of medication errors, nursing managers, head nurses, and nurse educators must work to treat and minimize these issues in order to reduce medication errors and improve patient safety in Saudi hospitals. It is critical to provide continuous education and on-the-job training for nurses in the hospital regarding medication administration.

Limitations of the study

This study's research approach cannot determine causality (cause and effect) because the cross-sectional study design is classified as being susceptible to bias in terms of eligibility criteria. As a result, participants who obtain differing insights, particularly while responding to the study questionnaire, may be overlooked. The use of this non-probability convenience sampling technique may result in the exclusion of broad segments of the community, resulting in underrepresentation of the population and a reduced capacity to generalize study findings.

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